

Rac-3k

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-101-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0825
Vial:	72	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 101 1 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/25/2021 3:21:14 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/23/2021 9:42:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.978	5063455	50.12	370316
2	10.950	5040192	49.88	331178

Asy-3k (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-106-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0825
Vial:	70	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 106 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/25/2021 2:49:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/23/2021 9:40:20 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.905	769411	6.12	56162
2	10.859	11808224	93.88	780853